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STRESS MANAGEMENT: A PRAGMATIC APPROACH TOWARDS ENHANCING EMPLOYEES' PRODUCTIVITY

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Abstract

Through this paper an attempt is being taken to discuss as how stress management can play a vital role in enhancing employees' productivity in an organization. With a view to systematizing the discussion on the topic referred to here, the entire paper is divided into three parts. The first part entitled Theoretical approach includes an introduction, meaning of stress and stress management, objective of the study, rationale of the study and methodology. The second part entitled Stress Management as a Pragmatic Approach to Enhancing employees' productivity is a comprehensive study where an emphasis is given to design some pragmatic techniques and ways of making an efficient and effective stress management system keeping in view to sustaining the employees' job stress as an ample source of their productivity. The third part entitled conclusion, where in addition to putting an overall conclusion some suitable suggestion are put forward in order to manage job stress of employees for the overall development of the organization. In fine, a model of stress management is given to make it understandable the system of designing and handling stress of employees in productive way.

Key Words: Stress, Stress Management, Employees' Productivity, Pragmatic approach, organization

Part: I

Theoretical Approach

1.1: Introduction

Stress is a common phenomenon in case of every employee. In most of the cases, stress adversely impact on employees' psychological and physiological aspects and consequently decreases the employees' performance. Ultimately this type of adverse job stress stands on the way of not only achieving the individual objective of employees, but also destroys the overall organizational objective of the organization. But, in practice, it is observed that due to devoid of systematic stress management; most of the employees have been suffering lot of mental and physical problem. Moreover, in top level management no proper policy is included in the constitution or rules and regulation of the organization regarding preventing and controlling stress of employees. That is why; there is a need to carry out a careful

research work on the topic referred here. So that, this type of research work can provide proper way with appropriate guidelines as how a system of stress management can be designed and by virtue of implementing this system how the top management can sustain the positive impact of stress in productive line and able to remove the negative impact of stress from the employees. Considering this objectives, this paper aims at discussing technique of sustain stress at optimum level, way of observing consequence of stress, technique of identifying level of stress, checking employees' behavior and approach to stress management.

1.2: In a very simple language stress is the body's nonspecific reaction to any demand made on it. Stress can also be defined as tension i.e. an outcome of anxiety and fear about a current event or a future want. Hans Selye, an early authority on the subject said that stress constitutes the factors effecting wear and tear on the body. In organization, this wear and tear is caused primarily by the body's unconscious mobilization of energy when an individual is confronted with organizational or work demands. So, the term stress normally refers to excessive stress caused by extraordinary demands, which cause us to lose something we desire, constraints, things that keep us from what we desire or opportunities.

1.3: Objective of the Study

The basic objective of the study is to design an efficient and effective stress management system, so that employees' effort can be productively utilized in satisfying their individual needs as well as organizational goals. Keeping in view this basic objective, the following specific objective has been taken under study:

- i. To examine the optimum level of employees job stress.
- ii. To observe the consequence of employees job stress.
- iii. To identify the different level of employees job stress.
- iv. To check the employees behavior in relation to stress.
- v. To design an effective approach to stress management.

1.4: Rationale of the Study

During classical period of management employees were use like a machine by force of some strict rules and regulations, where employees were not considered as human beings. But consequently it was realized that employees are human being having some feelings, desire, needs attitude and perceptions. Hence, without considering these human aspects no management cans successes at all. Therefore, during neoclassical period of management employees behavior, motivation and social needs etc are considered as an important aspect for successful management. In this connection, stress is a very much important dimensions of employees without considering which management measurably failed to design a successful management system and policy. Stress management system should be an integral part of every branch of management, such as, human resource management, marketing management, financial management, production and operation management etc. In the liberalization, privatization and globalization (LPG) period employees of every organization have to bear a heavy work load to survive in the competitive market situation. Such type of scenario leads to increase the stress level of employees. Simultaneously, inspite of having both the positive and negative impact of stress majority employee have been suffering adversely from negative impact from their job stress. Hence it is an urgent time to design an appropriate system of stress management. So that, employees will be free from any adverse effect likely to be arises from their job stress and they will able to capture potential fruitful benefits of stress for the betterment of both of their individual and organization. This facts and circumstances warrant a careful study on stress management.

1.5: Methodology

The study is based on both primary and secondary data. The primary data are collected by the technique of questionnaire. In doing so hundred number of different category of respondent are taken under study are shown below.

Table No: 1.1

List of Selected Respondent

SL No	Categories	Nos
1	Top executive from different private sector	10
2	Top executive from government sector	10
3	Middle level employees from private sector	10
4	Middle level employees from government sector	10
5	Lower level employees from private sector	10
6	Lower level employees from government sector	10
7	Owner of private sector Industry	10
8	Doctors	10
9	Psychologist	10
10	Intellectual Citizen	10
	Total No of Respondent	100

Source: Compile from field survey and personal interview

In order to elicit their views and attitudes different question were put pertaining to stress management. On the other hand, secondary data have been compiled from various books, journals and relevant websites. **Both primary and secondary data are analyzed** with a view to observing the various impacts and aspects of employees job stress and in the light of this analysis an attempt is being taken to design an effective system of stress management. In fine, a new model of case study is presented to understand the stress management in easy way.

Part: II

Stress Management as a pragmatic approach to enhancing employees' productivity:

In order to enhance employees' productivity, it is immensely important to manage the stress of employees in a successful way .Otherwise; it is not possible to utilize employees' skill, efficiency, experience and their talent for the purpose of achieving their personal goal as well as for organizational goals. On the other hand, the need of the managing stress of employees is arisen in every branch of management, such as Human resource management, Production management, Marketing management and Financial management. That is why, below an attempt is being taken to highlight various important dimensions of stress management to know its pragmatic approach.

2.1: Method of sustaining stress at optimum level:

Organizational life is quite stressful. In spite of happening so stress is not always unpleasant .To be successful every people is to bear a certain level of stress without which life will become dull, monotonous .Of course ,the term stress normally implies excessive workload which leads to heavy tension and mental anxiety. That is why; there is a need of sustaining the level of stress in optimum level. So that this optimum level of stress helps the employees in enhancing their productivities for the accomplishment of their individual goals of life as well as help in fulfilling organizational goal also. Therefore, keeping in view to sustaining the employees stress in optimum level, the top management should very carefully observe the increasing rate of stress up to which the stress can be define as constructive stress and beyond which level of stress it can be defined as destructive stress. Below the figure no 2.1 depicts how the optimum level of stress can be determined by the two faces of stress.

Figure : 2.1

Constructive stress (Eustress) acts in a positive manner for the individual and the organization ,e.g. ,winning a contest , or falling in love.Eustress can indicate a situation where the individual is in balance or within tolerable limits.The figure shows that how to moderate amount of stress can act in a constructive or energizing way.Moderate stress can increase effort , stimulate creativity and encourage diligence in one’s work. It can be equated with tension that causes you to work hard before exams, pay attention in class , and completed projects and assignments on time. The same positive result of stress can be found in work place. Destructive stress (Distress) is not healthy for the individual or organization. Distress would indicate effects that are out of balance or outside the tolerance limits. Excessive stress may lead to overload and break down a person’s physical and mental systems.Performance can suffer as people experience illness brought on by very intense stress and react to high stress through absenteeism, turnover, errors, accidents and dissatisfaction and reduced performance.

2.2: Questionnaire analysis

Q.1 According to you how many top executives are interested as well as able to sustain stress of their employees at optimum level?

Against putting this question to 100 respondent following percentage of different opinions have been obtained

Table No: 2. 1

Distribution of Respondent

Most	Average	Less	Neutral
11%	28%	52%	9%

Source :Compiled from questionnaire and field survey

The above distribution of percentage is shown in the following diagram.

Explanation: From the feedback obtained from hundred respondent it is seen that more than half respondent i.e. 52% are of the opinion that only a less number of top management executives are in a position to sustain their job stress of employee in optimum level. According to them most of the top executives are very much busy with their routine work and they cannot spare any time for thinking to design a technique of measuring the optimum level of stress of their employees. On the other hand, according to 28% only average number of top management executives is interested for sustaining level of their employees stress at optimum level. According to them most of these top management executives are not accordingly trained up and efficient to design the measuring technique of optimum level of employees stress. According to 11% of respondent most of the top executives are found to be failure in determining the optimum level of their employees stress. According to 11% of respondent it is because of the fact that most of the executives are not force for doing so by any act and law. In our questionary 9% respondent are found to be neutral.

2.3:Way of observing Consequence of Stress : Regarding stress top management should perpetually monitoring its consequence. So that by no means negative consequence occurred from the employee stress in the organization. In this regards it is to be mention that stress is of two types such as eustress and distress.”The idea of eustress or healthy stress was first proposed by Richard Lajarus (1974).It is a condition where in the individual feels a positive drive and wants to fulfill his /her needs and achieve his/her goals. The level of modification is high. The individual is optimistic about achievement and the situation appears not only challenging but also stimulating. Stress disappears when the need is fulfil and success achieved.”On the other hand, when employees of an organization face a condition of distress than they fill a sense of helplessness about their target to be achieved which is shown in the figure 2.3.

Figure : 2.3

Questionnaire Analysis:

Q.2 According to you how many organizations follow the way of observing consequence of employees job stress?

Against putting this question to 100 respondent following percentage of different opinion has been obtained

Table: 2.2

Distribution of Respondent

Most	Average	Less	Neutral
19%	35%	44%	2%

Figure: 2.4

Explanation: Out of the feedback of 100 respondents , it reveals that very less number of organization (19%)mostly monitoring the consequence of their employees job stress, whereas , 44% respondents said that less number of organization only give serious attention on the consequence arise from their employees job stress. On the other hand, 33% respondent agrees that average number of organization take into their consideration the consequence of their respective organizational employees' job stress. Hence ,it is founded most of the organization ignore the consequence aspect of employees job stress , which leads to increase the level of employee job stress more than enough and ultimately employee has to suffer a lot of physical as well as mental troubles.

2.4: Technique of Identifying different Level of Stress: Identification of level of stress is one of the immensely important aspects to be observed by the top management. Different employees may suffer from stress at different level .If top management accordingly does not detect this level than it may gradually increase up to a danger level which adversely impact on both employees and organizational level. In this connection it is to be mention that stress is occurred in three different levels. There are different symptoms of different level. That is why , management should continuously monitor the existence of this symptom for the purpose of knowing the level of stress suffered by different employees. So that ,accordingly management can take initiative for detecting the cause and adopt remedial measures for permanent solution. Every responsible manager should know the different symptom of stress of different level as depicted in the following figure.

Figure : 2.5

Q.3 Do you think that any attempt is taken by your organization to formulate any specific technique for identifying the level of employees stress?

Table: 2.3

Distribution of Respondent

Most	Aaverage	Less	Neutral
21%	29%	45%	5%

Explanation: There is a need of formulating and adopting proper technique for detecting the level of employees stress. Otherwise, employees stress may adversely impact on organizational working environment. But the lamentable matter is that only 21 % respondent is of the opinion that their organization adopt such type of techniques, whereas ,45% respondents said that very lessly their organization follow any technique for identifying the level of their employees stress. On the other hand, the opinion of 29% respondent are that average number of organization are interested for formulating as well as applying the techniques to identify the level of their employees stress. Out of this distribution of respondent feedback it can be concluded that very less number of organization i.e. 21% mostly formulate specific technique for identifying the level of their employees job stress.

2.5: Guidelines of Checking Employees Behaviors in relation to Stress: In practical circumstances there is a direct relationship in between stress and employees behavior. Hence, it is a prime duty of top management as well as concerned managers to pay serious attention towards the day to day behavior of their employees to know whether this behavior is the manifestation of their abnormal stress. In this regard psychologist has divided people into two broad categories depending upon the behavior pattern of employees. These are Type A individuals and Type B individuals which is presented with respective personalities respond to stress in the following table.

Table: 2.4

Types of Individuals

Type A Individual	Type B Individual
Chronic Struggle with the environment	Balanced interplay with the environment
Hard driving (over achiever)	Rational approach to achievement
Time urgency (hyper responsive)	Relaxed
Hostility	Positive interpersonal relations
Workaholics	Balanced between work and events

“Friedman and Rosenman (1974) identified type A personality when they observed recurrent personality behavior patterns having tendency of hurry sickness in their patients who were identified to be suffering from premature heart disease. Besides being concerned with time deadlines and commitments ,most type A persons are competitive and aggressive manner .The top management can follow the following guidelines for checking the Type A behavior .Restrain from being centre of attention by constantly and continuously talking. Try to take charge of your time directed life by making yourself aware of it. Reflect and assess the cause of your hurry sickness. Is there a need to feel important? Understand and be clear that majority of your work and social life do not really require universal acclaim. Broaden yourself. Indulge in outdoor activities such as theatre, reading, music, games, etc.Try not to make necessary appointments and unachievable deadlines. Protect your time by learning to say no. Does something relax you. Try to make yourself aware of your behavior and its impact on others. Take time off to develop and social relationships.

Q.4 Do your organization provide any guidelines for checking employees behavior in relation to stress?

Table: 2. 5

Distribution of Respondent

Most	Average	Less	Neutral
6%	17%	68%	9%

Explanation: Employees behave is the external expression of their internal feelings. Most of the psychologist comes to conclusion that stress of employees is manifested by their behaviour .Hence, it is essential to check the employees behavior in relation to stress. But in our questionnaire 68% respondent is of the opinion that their organization lessly provide specific guideline for checking their employees behavior in relation to stress and 17% respondent said that averagely their organization follow such type of guidelines for the checking of their employees behavior in relation to stress where only 6% respondent agree

that their organization mostly follow such type of guidelines. Out of this explanation it is understood that employee's behavior is very rarely taken into consideration by the top management in relation to employees stress.

2.6: **Effective Approach to Managing Stress:** Every manager should remember that without stress challenge is nothing because stress is a state of mind which drives individuals to take on difficult situation. By managing this difficult situation managers as well as employees will be able to make their life to easy and uncomplicated .In front of every manager there are two ways of managing stress by one way managers can prevent stress from developing to the extent that one becomes non-functional. By the second way managers are to develop a mechanism to get back to normal as quickly as one can and not to continue in a state of stress for too long. Developing a positive attitude towards life by rational and logical thinking and realizing that one's perception can often distort reality is essential to handling stress effectively. The situation may not be as bad as it may seem to be and failure is not an irreversible situation. It is not possible or even necessary to succeed all the time. One failed effort doesn't imply that the individual is no good. Even world champions sometimes lose the first round of match to an unseeded player.

Q.5 Is there any effective approach to be implemented by your organization for managing stress?

Table :2.6

Distribution of Respondent

Most	Average	Less	Neutral
32%	51%	14%	3%

Explanation: This question was asked to 100 respondents to know whether their organization implement any effective approach to manage their employees job stress. Against this question only 32% respondent agree that effective approach is formulated by their organization mostly to manage stress. On the other hand , more than half respondents i.e.51% is of the opinion that at average rate their organization are interested to implement effective approach to manage their employees jib stress, whereas ,14% respondent said that very lessely their organization adopt some effective approach to manage their employees job stress. The feedback of the respondents reveals that most of the organization (51%) still not interested to adopt any effective approach to manage their employee's job stress in each and every step of their day to day functioning.

Part: III

3.0: **Conclusion:** Throughout the above explanation along with the feedback obtain from the one hundred respondent it can be concluded that stress need not necessarily be avoided as because it is not at all possible to have a general as well as organizational life without a certain minimum amount of stress. Stress is an open and democratic process as because every individual is aware, conscious and knows when he/she under goes stress , its causes and implications in human system. That is why, prime duty of the top management is to detect the cause and effect of stress and manage the same accordingly. In this connection, it is to be mention that symptoms are minified amongst employees as irritability , stuttering and

Figure: 3.1

stammering , lack of concentration ,restlessness , lack of appetite and high tended tangency to smoke and drink as mention in earlier discussion. Management should attempt to utilized the positive impact of their employees job stress towards the productive purpose and tries to convert the negative impact of their employee job stress also towards the productive purpose by adopting various approaches such as exercise ,follow good diet habit , know when to pull back , put the stressful situation into perspective , recognize employees limitation , tolerant ,pursue outside diversion , avoid artificial control etc.By virtue of the above approaches, so that the management can establish a peaceful organizational condition, work culture atmosphere, homely environment ,fearless leadership style,

democratic climate ,team spirit etc to free from their employees to free from their employees from any negative impact of job stress. Only on that situation the organizational life of employees as well as executives can be use with satisfaction and productive way, which is depicted in the following model of job stress.

Explanation of Figure Above:

In the stress managing process, the first step is the identification of employees' who have been suffering from stress. For that purpose the management can entrust a duty and responsibility to every departmental heads to detect the stressful employees. Accordingly after identifying the stressful employees the departmental head should send this list to top management. After that, the duty of the top management is to identify the cause of stress. In doing so ,the top management should constitute a Stress Redressal Committee(SRC) which is to be formed with some specialist such as psychologist, doctor and researcher along with experienced top executive. The responsibility of the committee is not only detecting the stress but also identify its impact whether positive or negative. It is gratifying to mention that identifying stressful employees, their causes and impact, infact is a very difficult task to be performed by the management. That is why, adequate attention should be paid in doing this task. Immediate after detecting the impact of stress the top management should perform the following two functions.

1. Positive impact of stress should be channelized by motivating and recognizing these concern employees towards the productive purpose.
2. Management should seriously adopt some remedial measures for solving the problem of employees who have been suffering from negative impact by virtue of provision of meditation, exercise etc. So that, those employees can also free from negative impact of stress.

This way, the top management should emphasis much more attention on converting both employees suffering negative and positive impact towards a Stress Free Zone(SFC) where employ will fearless from stress. It is to be mentioned that only from this zone employees' as well as organization can fulfill their respective goals and accordingly became successful and satisfaction.

References :

- 1.Pandey , S. (2013) , "A study on Work Stress , Cause ,Symptoms and Impact on Health" ,International Journals of Innovation Research and Studies , Volume 2 No.5 , pp.243-259
- 2.Shukla ,H. and Garg ,R (2013) " A Study on Stress Management Among the Employees of Nationalised Banks " , Voice of Research , Volume 2 No.3 ,pp.72-75
- 3.Bhat , A. and Kumar , A (2011) Management Principles ,Processes and Practices ,Oxford university Press, New-delhi
- 4.Mondy Wayne , R. (2010) Human Resource Management , Pearson Education ,New -Delhi
5. Rao , P.S.V. (2009) Human Resource Management Text and Cases, Excel Books ,New-Delhi
- 6.Certo , S.C. and Certo ,S.T. (2010) , Modern Management Concepts and Skills ,PHI Learning ,New-Delhi